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NEXTWAY: OPEN SOURCE LAST MILE DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR MSMEs

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Acceptance Page:

This paper prepared by **ALDRIN A. NAVARRO** with the title: “**NEXTWAY: OPEN SOURCE LAST MILE DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR MSMEs**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

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Biographical Sketch

Aldrin Navarro is a multifaceted Software Engineer with over 9 years of professional IT experience. His experience on all stages of software development along with his special interest on human-computer interaction helped him mold an understanding of connecting with and delivering solutions to his clients.

Aldrin earned his B.S. Computer Science degree at the University of the Philippines Cebu in 2015. While at the university, he also worked as a student research assistant for the then Department of Computer Science. In 2014, Aldrin presented the department's research "Supporting the Health System on Dengue using an Agent-based Epidemic Model" and along with the poster "An agent-based epidemic model for dengue simulation in the Philippines" which won the best conference poster. The research team is composed of two university professors Prof. Kurt Junshean Espinosa, and Dr. Florian Miksch, a visiting professor from TU Wien, Institute for Analysis and Scientific Computing, Vienna, Austria, and a fellow research student assistant Katrina Casera. Aldrin gained significant academic research skills as well as a once in a lifetime opportunity to work with a highly dedicated team in advancing epidemic modeling in the local scene.

Aldrin is a Software Engineer and Tech Lead at Newlogic (2019 – present); Software Developer at Channelfix LLC (2014 – 2019); IT Consultant at Regal Group (2018); Web Developer at Enhance Visa (2016); and a Software Developer Intern at Crowd Metric Solutions, Inc (2014).

Aldrin's professional growth also includes completing Google IT Automation with Python Specialization Professional Certificate and earning the certifications AWS Certified Cloud Practitioner, Microsoft Certified Azure Fundamentals, and TryHackMe Junior Penetration Tester.

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Finally, to God, for imparting to me the courage, wisdom, and patience to get me through all the sacrifice and hard work necessary for this endeavor. Jehovah Jireh. All of this, I offer to you.

Dedication

To my family. To Josel.
Thank you for unconditional support.

To Prof Kurt Junshean Espinosa,
for inspiring me to push the boundaries.
Rest in peace.

To the wise men that came before us and to God.
For all these things require the help of God and fortune.

ABSTRACT

As the industry of micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in the Philippines grew over the years and contributed much to the economy, opportunities and challenges to the last mile delivery came along with the demand. No business-to-customer (B2C) transactions are complete without product fulfillment. Last mile delivery is the last leg of moving goods from hubs to customers in the supply chain. Such services existed in the Philippines as third-party logistics (3PL) solutions. While MSMEs may simply tap into these 3PLs, this study has proposed and demonstrated that open-source solutions could integrate into their existing logistics and delivery teams.

The Nextway project has developed cost-effective and reliable solutions to aid small companies, drivers, and customers. Considering the economic aspect of MSMEs, a significant capital expense was found unnecessary for adopting their last mile delivery solution. Various literature has proven that a last mile delivery system is a considerable asset and investment a business in the scale of MSME could acquire. In particular, the pilot implementation of this study for the client has solved the challenges of digitization of data, receiving orders and tracking physical packages into warehouses, designation of delivery personnel, tracking of the loaded packages into the vehicle, and providing meaningful information to drivers. The Nextway backend has utilized the open-source Odoo community edition as a provider of the enterprise resource planning (ERP) aspect of the business.

The pilot implementation of the developed system also highlighted the importance of using Metodología para la selección de sistemas ERP (MSSE) or System Selection Methodology for careful system selection. In addition, the Enterprise System Experience Cycle was selected as the overall guiding methodology and adoption assessment. This study has contributed to the research and practical use of the provided system designs for both on-premises and cloud service provider deployments, whichever future potential adopters need. Along with those were suggestions for future work, such as a cloud-edge continuum approach to further provide reliable services to the drivers and customers in rural areas with limited network connectivity.